

Enhancing Lecturer Performance Through Servant Leadership and Professional Competence: A Study in Central Kalimantan Private Universities

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the effect of servant leadership and professional competence on lecturer performance in private universities in Central Kalimantan. The data analysis technique in this study used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis. The findings showed that lecturer performance in private universities in Central Kalimantan is determined by three main aspects, namely education and teaching, research, and community service, with education and teaching as the dominant indicator. Organizational commitment is more influenced by affective commitment, followed by normative and continuance. Servant leadership does not directly influence lecturer performance, as lecturers focus more on teaching and research. In contrast, professional competence directly affects lecturer performance, especially through developing knowledge, professional skills, and initiatives that improve communication and learning methods. The study results are expected to be utilized by university leaders to improve lecturer performance by developing servant leadership and professional competence. In addition, the results of this study can also be the basis for formulating human resource development policies in higher education to be more effective and sustainable.

KEYWORDS: Performance, Servant Leadership, Professional Leadership

1. INTRODUCTION

The current implementation of lecturer certification must go through tests and various skills verifications. This phenomenon has the effect that only lecturers who reach a certain level of professional competence can receive certification. Skills, responsibilities, and abilities in the execution of tasks can meet the demands of the role and expertise of lecturers. These can predict lecturer performance levels, i.e., motives, self-concept, and character. Individual competence in skills and knowledge can be developed through education, while motive competence can be obtained during selection (Sarwani et al., 2021).

There is a difference between competence, knowledge, skills, and abilities. Knowledge refers to information about a subject's theoretical and practical understanding, which a person acquires through experience or education. In contrast, skills, on the other hand, refer to the application of data or information and can be tested to measure the quantity and quality of individual performance (Schrimpe et al., 2016). This can be completed within a specified time limit. At the same time, ability refers to the

adequacy of strength to complete a task, especially the physical and mental qualities needed to carry out activities.

Lisbijanto's research (2014) shows that market orientation, learning orientation, and financial literacy positively relate to knowledge competence, innovation, and performance of small and medium textile industries in Java and Bali. Knowledge competence plays an important role in driving innovation and improving resource performance. Learning orientation creates knowledge competencies that can be used to improve innovation. Another study by Yusuf (2014) found that competence has a positive and significant effect on performance, while organizational culture has a positive but insignificant effect. However, the study of Yunaningsih et al. (2021) in West Java shows that competence has no significant effect on lecturer performance, indicating that lecturer performance cannot be evaluated directly through competence.

The performance of lecturers in the LLDIKTI XI Kalimantan region needs special attention. Research shows that human resource competencies, which include theoretical abilities and practical skills, are essential. Ideal competence

is supported by orientation, quality, problem-solving skills, planning, teamwork, and self-learning capacity (Supriyono, 2017). Every individual has potential that must be considered to improve human resource competencies. Seven competence areas must be developed: pedagogical competence, techniques and information, management/administration, curriculum, scientific (research and publication), evaluation, and personal competence (Ali & Si, 2015). Improving the competence of lecturers in this region is in line with the efforts of LLDIKTI XI to facilitate the improvement of the quality of higher education implementation.

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Previous research by Rianto et al. (2020) using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method shows that transformational leadership, competence, and work motivation positively and significantly influence lecturer performance, both partially and simultaneously. Similar results were found by Adi (2018), who revealed a significant correlation between professional competence, effective learning, and performance. Using the Self-Determination Theory perspective, another study by Lee and Bai (2014) examined the relationship between perceived principal learning support and psychological need satisfaction, organizational commitment, and change-oriented work behavior. The results showed that principals' perceived learning support directly influenced psychological need satisfaction, including autonomy, competence, and relatedness, and positively impacted organizational commitment and change-oriented work behavior.

This study aims to analyze the effect of servant leadership and professional competence on lecturer performance in private universities in Central Kalimantan. The study results are expected to provide practical and theoretical benefits for developing science and policy. Practically, these results can be utilized by higher education leaders to improve lecturer performance through developing servant leadership and professional competence. Theoretically, this study analyzes the effect of servant leadership and competence on lecturer performance mediated

by organizational commitment. In addition, for stakeholders, the results of this study can be the basis for formulating human resource development policies in higher education to be more effective and sustainable.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Human resource management (HRM), as a key to creating and developing a productive workforce, is at the center of a debate about its impact on business competitiveness Lepak et al., (2006). According to Jiang et al. (2012), Human Resource Management (HRM) is a practice that promotes motivation, employee effort, knowledge, skills, abilities, and opportunities that generate favorable conditions for the development of resources and capabilities that create value for the institution/organization. Lecturers are a source of institutional competitive advantage. However, it is also very important to answer the main indicators that underlie us in showing and proving the importance of human resources and human resource management practices to achieve organizational success.

Based on the relationship between variables in this study, the approach refers to the Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory, which asserts that resources are valuable assets for organizations in creating competitive advantage. According to RBV, organizations with strategic resources will be superior to competitors who do not have them. However, not all resources are considered strategic, as competitors can easily obtain material resources. Strategic resources must meet the criteria of valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable. In this case, human resources meet these criteria. Ownership of strategic resources enables organizations to develop sustainable competitive advantages that impact long-term profits (Supriadi, 2025).

Job Performance comes from the term "work performance" or "actual performance", which refers to the quality and quantity of work a person does in carrying out tasks according to their responsibilities. Performance is important for organizations because it reflects their effectiveness and success. A successful organization has individuals with good performance and quality. According to Hasibuan (2007), performance results from work achieved by someone based on skills, experience, seriousness, and time. Performance has also shifted from the concept of productivity, which was originally used to measure the ability of individuals or organizations to achieve goals. The new productivity paradigm emphasizes measuring actual performance, including efficiency and intangible dimensions, which reflect the organization's overall performance.

Rummler and Brache (1995) state that there are three interrelated levels of performance in organizations: organizational performance, process performance, and individual performance. Organizational performance refers to achieving outcomes influenced by organizational goals,

design, and management. Process performance focuses on the effectiveness and efficiency of the stages in producing a product or service, depending on the process's purpose, design, and management. Meanwhile, individual performance refers to the achievement of work results or the effectiveness of employees in carrying out tasks, which is influenced by goals, design, job management, and individual characteristics. These three levels are interconnected and influence each other, so the organization's success in achieving the desired results depends on optimizing performance at each level.

Performance measurement is an evaluation process to assess progress in achieving predetermined goals, including the efficiency of resource use and the effectiveness of actions taken. It involves comparing the results of activities with predetermined targets. Organizations must distinguish between performance outcomes and personality measurements and ensure that performance measurements are carried out appropriately. According to Al Mehrzi and Singh (2016), performance is the level of success of a person during a certain period in carrying out tasks based on agreed work standards, targets, or criteria. In addition, Law Number 14 of 2005 states that lecturers are professional educators and scientists tasked with transforming, developing, and disseminating science, technology, and art to improve human resources quality.

Miner (1988) identified four main indicators in assessing a person's performance: quality, quantity, use of time at work, and ability to cooperate. Quality includes errors, defects, and care in completing work, where good results indicate minimal errors and conform to standards. Quantity refers to the work produced in a given period, reflecting individual productivity. Use of time at work includes attendance, tardiness, and effective work time, indicating an individual's efficiency in utilizing time. Teamwork refers to skills in building relationships and collaborating with colleagues to create synergy within the organization. The first two indicators relate to work outcomes, while the other two relate to individual behavior. Performance measurement focuses on the individual level.

Ideal leadership places life as a service, not just a career. The need for servant leaders is growing, and the spirit of service must be embedded in every member of society. Sincere service brings happiness as an added value to the service provided. Effective leaders are those who realize employees' potential and take steps to develop them for the betterment of the organization. According to Angga (2021), credible leadership can be seen from the leader's behavior in supporting organizational members. The most effective type of leadership today is collaborative leadership, which focuses on problem-solving and developing individual professional abilities to create an optimal work situation and support the growth of each organization member.

Traditional leadership structures that focus on an agent perspective, where individuals are seen serving their self-interest and being competitive, are no longer considered adequate in today's work environment. Therefore, leadership theories with a relational perspective emphasizing self-actualization and cooperation have emerged (Lotje et al., 2017). One approach that has gained widespread attention is Servant Leadership, which is described as a holistic strategy in which leaders focus on the social, emotional, and ethical aspects of relationships with followers (Liden et al., 2014). Servant Leadership aims to help followers develop skills to achieve greater success (Liden et al., 2008). In contrast to other approaches prioritizing leader support, Servant Leadership stands out because it emphasizes leaders serving followers.

According to Law No. 14/2005 on Teachers and Lecturers Article 1 Paragraph 10, competence is a set of knowledge, skills, and behaviors that teachers and lecturers must possess, live, and master in carrying out their professionalism. Competence includes a combination of knowledge (thinking power), skills (physical power), and attitudes (heart power), which are manifested in action. Emron et al. (2016) state that competence is an individual's ability to carry out work correctly based on knowledge, skills, and attitudes. According to Spencer and Spencer (in Emron et al., 2016), competence is a basic characteristic of individuals that has a causal relationship with effective work performance in certain situations. George Klemp (in Emron et al., 2016) added that competence includes personal aspects that affect effective and high-quality performance, not just technical abilities but also individual characteristics that determine work success.

Competence is defined as a fundamental characteristic of an individual that is causally related to effective and superior performance in a job or situation (Spencer & Spencer, 1993). To achieve adequate performance, threshold competence is required, which guides employee selection, task transfer planning, performance evaluation, and human resource development. Competence includes the knowledge, experience, and skills needed to fulfill the role's demands according to industry standards. Mitrani defines competence as an individual's fundamental characteristics associated with effective and superior performance in a particular job. Competencies include aspects that affect individual success in carrying out tasks and determine the effectiveness of employee performance in various work situations.

Each employee has characteristics based on the abilities he must master through certain processes and stages so that his competence is useful in the world of work. McClelland (1987) developed a series of personality tests to assess whether someone is a high achiever. He also introduced the practice of competency testing in the civil service recruitment process in 1973, assuming that such tests

could identify individual competencies (Raven, 2001). Competence comes from skills, which means proficiency, ability, and authority. Competence indicates a person's behavioral skills or excellence in carrying out tasks. Competence includes proficiency in carrying out tasks, ability to complete work, and employee responsibility. Hr & Aithal (2020) emphasized that competence is important in achieving optimal performance.

3. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Lecturer performance is a professional in staff education and scientists with the main task of transforming, developing, and disseminating science, technology, and art through education, research, and community service. The campus is a sacred institution that plays a role in discovery or innovation activities, conceptualizing ideas, disseminating science, and disseminating truthful empirical data and facts. Indicators: Carrying out Education and Teaching, Research and Development, And Community Service.

This study refers to the recommendations of research results according to (Awadh et al., 2014) in his research that "The employee performance would be considered as the backbone of the organization as it leads to its development effectively". Employee performance is the backbone of effective organizational development. Based on this statement, the low performance of construction service companies is caused by the relatively low performance of experts. Ling et al. (2015), in their research "The trickle-down effect of servant leadership on frontline employee service behavior, and performance," stated that the trickle-down effect of servant leadership on frontline employee service behavior and performance, its nature strengthens a relationship where Servant Leadership also greatly affects performance and provides positive and significant value results affect performance. Servant Leadership Affects Lecturer Performance.

In some cases, the definition of competence is considered very positive, and in others, it is considered a lack of specification. During this time, several competencies allocated in each course showed interest in verifying whether lecturers considered the competencies allocated during teaching, lecturers also considered the relationship between competencies and content. In some cases, these two elements are contrasted.

Another aspect commented on was the imbalance between specific competencies directly related to the course and general competencies. In contrast, another study on lecturer quality assessment showed that competencies related to interpersonal skills were higher than those related to professional development.

Korytkowski (2017) "Competences-based performance model of multi-skilled workers with learning and forgetting". Competencies affect performance and

experience non-linearly, so planning models that attempt to manage workforce development through task assignments are difficult to solve. Based on the explanation of the theory of competency theory and the results of previous research, it can be concluded that lecturer competence affects lecturer performance. Not only does it affect lecturer performance, but it also affects the learning process associated with students and university rankings.

Previous research proved that servant leadership positively impacts competitive advantage, employee empowerment, and organizational learning. Employee empowerment has a positive impact on competitive advantage, and organizational learning has a positive impact on competitive advantage. A longitudinal study using online surveys was conducted and found that top management commitment and intellectual models have a direct impact on human resource management and environmental performance. The results also support a mediated relationship.

4. RESEARCH METHOD

4.1 Population and Research Sample

The population in this study were all lecturers in Central Kalimantan under the auspices of the Higher Education Service Institution (LLDIKTI) Region XI Kalimantan in the 2020/2021 academic year. Researchers took a sample of 5% of the total lecturers in each college or university in the region. The sample size was calculated using the Slovin formula, and based on the calculation results, a sample size of 232 lecturers was obtained. Thus, the sample in this study was 232 lecturers spread across various universities in Central Kalimantan.

4.2 Data Analysis Technique

The analysis technique uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis. SEM processing using the AMOS 24 program.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Research Results

Central Kalimantan Province has 23 private universities, 10 located in Palangkaraya, while 13 are in regencies. Of these 23 universities, all lecturers have an average of S2 education, and only a few universities have lecturers with S3 education. It is clear that there is a low interest in continuing to a higher level, and, of course, the lecturer has several reasons for this.

Characteristics of Research Respondents. There were 235 respondents in this study, consisting of lecturers from various universities in the Kalimantan region. The characteristics of respondents in this study include gender, age, latest education, and income, which are presented in detail in the following table.

Table 1. Characteristics of Research Respondents

No	Category	Description	Total	Frequency
1	Gender	Male	150	63,8%
		Female	85	36,2%
2	Age	20 – 30 Years	75	31,9%
		31 – 40 Years	65	27,6%
		41 – 50 Years	45	19,2%
		50 > Years	50	21,2%
3	Last Education	Doctoral Degree (S3)	35	14,9%
		Masters Degree (S2)	180	76,6%
		Bachelor Degree (S1)	20	8,5%
4	Income	< 5.000.000	85	36,2%
		5.000.000 – 10.000.000	115	48,9%
		> 10.000.0000	35	14,9%

Source: Primary data processed

Based on the data obtained, the gender of lecturer respondents in Central Kalimantan Universities is dominated by men with a percentage of 63.8%, while female lecturers are 36.2%. In terms of age, the dominating age group is 20-30 years old at 31.9%, while the lowest age group is 41-50 years old with 19.2%, indicating that respondents are at an age that is mature enough to provide relevant answers to the questionnaire. Regarding the latest education, most respondents have a master's degree, with a percentage of 76.6%. In comparison, only 8.5% have a bachelor's degree, indicating they have an adequate educational background to answer the questionnaire. Meanwhile, in terms of income, the dominating group is respondents with an income of

Rp5,000,000-Rp10,000,000 at 48.9%, while those who earn more than Rp10,000,000 are the least with a percentage of 14.9%.

Research Instrument Test. To obtain data to test the hypothesis, this study used a tool in the form of a questionnaire. Before conducting further analysis, it is necessary to test the research instrument, namely the validity and reliability test of four variables, namely Servant Leadership (X1), Competence (X2), Commitment (Y1), and Lecturer Performance (Y2). The results of the analysis are presented in the Appendix and summarized in the following Table:

Table 2. Research Instrument Test

Variable	Indicator	Validity	Reliability
Servant Leadership (X1)	X1.1	0,9	0,937
	X1.2	0,916	
	X1.3	0,928	
	X1.4	0,927	
Competence (X2)	X2.1	0,880	0,865
	X2.2	0,916	
	X2.3	0,868	
Commitment (Y1)	Y1.1	0,906	0,878
	Y1.2	0,914	
	Y1.3	0,876	
Lecturer Performance (Y2)	Y2.1	0,896	0,894
	Y2.2	0,909	
	Y2.3	0,922	

Source: Primary data processed

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Table 2 above shows that all indicators have a correlation value above 0.3. This indicates that all question items on the four research variables are valid. The four variables have a coefficient value above 0.5 from the Cronbach Alpha coefficient value, so the four research variables are declared reliable. Thus, respondents who measure the five variables, namely Servant Leadership (X1), Competence (X2), Commitment (Y1), and Lecturer Performance (Y2), are said to be valid and reliable, and the measurement data using the questionnaire is suitable for use.

Assumption Testing in SEM. Data analysis in this study was carried out to test the hypothesis using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method. Before the analysis results can be interpreted, three assumptions must be met, namely the assumptions of linearity, normality, and the absence of outliers. The first assumption tested was linearity, which was carried out using the Curve Fit method and calculated with the help of SPSS software version 25. Based on the test results, it can be seen that the relationship between variables shows a significant linear model, with a sig value (p-value) smaller than 0.05, which means that the linearity assumption has been met. Therefore, this study's four relationships between variables are linear so that the SEM method can be used in data analysis.

The second assumption is the multivariate normal assumption. Data normality is evaluated using a critical ratio skewness value of ± 2.58 at a significance level of 0.01 (1%). Data is said to be normally distributed if the critical ratio skewness value is below ± 2.58 (Ghozali, 2005). Multivariate normal results are presented in the Appendix. The reference used is that if the multivariate normal does not meet, the principle of parsimony is used, where the multivariate normal is considered fulfilled because of the large number of samples

used. Based on the calculation results of the Assessment of Normality table in the Appendix, all indicators of the critical ratio skewness value are not located between ± 2.58 . However, based on the principle of parsimony, it can be said that the data from all indicators are multivariate, normally distributed, and suitable for use.

The third assumption is the assumption of no outliers. To test for the presence or absence of outliers, the Mahalanobis distance (Md) is used. Mahalanobis distance measures the proximity of the "average" data center point to each observation point. In this case, the observation point is the respondent's questionnaire number. Multivariate outliers were examined using the Mahalanobis criterion at the $p < 0.001$. The Mahalanobis distance is evaluated using χ^2 the free degree equal to the number of parameters in the model, namely = 53, where the statistical table obtained 37.28. The decision-making rules are: if the Md of the observation point is > 37.28 , it is stated that the observation point is an outlier, while if the Md of the observation point is < 37.28 , it is stated that the observation point is not an outlier. Based on the Mahalanobis distance table (Appendix), it can be seen that the observation points have Md values between 12.522 and 32.116, all of which are smaller than 37.28, so it is concluded that all observation points are not outliers. Thus, the outlier assumption is met.

Hypothesis Testing Results on Structural Models. Structural model testing is carried out to test two hypotheses, which include the relationship between variables and both direct and indirect effects. The complete results of testing the relationship between variables in this study are presented below:

Table 3. Results of Research Hypothesis Testing (Direct and Indirect Influence)

Hipotesis	Pengaruh Langsung	Koefisien Jalur	Standard Error	Critical Ratio	P-Value	Keterangan
Pengaruh Langsung						
H1	Servant Leadership → Kinerja Dosen	0,034	0,040	0,786	0,432	Tidak Signifikan
H2	Kompetensi → Kinerja Dosen	0,533	0,086	6,531	<0,000	Significance

Source: Primary data processed, 2022

The results of hypothesis testing show that the first hypothesis in this study states that Servant Leadership has a positive and significant effect on lecturer performance in private universities in Central Kalimantan. However, the results of hypothesis testing using the SEM approach show that this effect is insignificant, with a path coefficient of 0.034 and a CR value of 0.786. Because the CR value is smaller than 1.96, the critical value of the Z table is at 5% alpha, and

these results indicate that servant leadership has no significant effect on lecturer performance. Based on this analysis, it can be concluded that the first hypothesis is not proven or cannot be accepted, which means that Servant Leadership is not a significant factor in improving lecturer performance in the context of this study.

The second hypothesis in this study states that professional competence has a positive and significant effect

on lecturer performance in private universities in Central Kalimantan. The results of hypothesis testing using the SEM approach show that professional competence has a significant effect with a path coefficient of 0.533 and a CR value of 6.531. Since the CR value is greater than 1.96, the critical value is at 5% alpha, and there is sufficient empirical evidence to accept the hypothesis. This indicates that professional competence positively and significantly influences lecturer performance. The positive coefficient indicates that the higher the professional competence of lecturers, the higher the performance of lecturers, which means that professional competence is an important factor in improving lecturer performance.

5.2 Discussion of the Research Results

The following discusses research on improving lecturer performance through Servant Leadership and professional competence. Based on the analysis, Servant Leadership is reflected by four main indicators: service, trust, credibility, and vision. The most dominant indicator in reflecting Servant Leadership is vision, which shows that the leader's vision is important in implementing a servant leadership model in Higher Education. Meanwhile, the service indicator is the lowest in shaping Servant Leadership. However, overall, the other three indicators, namely trust, credibility, and vision, are statistically proven to reflect the concept of Servant Leadership well so that they can support the implementation of effective leadership in the academic environment.

Empirically, the indicator with the highest average value is credibility, followed by service. This indicates that leaders' credibility in providing services to subordinates is a positive factor in applying the Servant Leadership model in the Higher Education environment. This result is reinforced by descriptive analysis, which shows that the average value of each indicator, namely service, trust, credibility, and vision, is in the "agree" category. This research supports the opinion of Chiniara (2015), which suggests that Servant Leadership consists of four main factors: service, trust, credibility, and vision, as measured through the Servant Leadership Assessment Instrument (SLAI). This means that a leadership style that focuses on serving, organizing, and managing subordinates is important in improving lecturer performance. Respondents' perceptions of Servant Leadership reflect how this leadership model is applied in academic organizations.

Competence in this study refers to respondents' perceptions of the abilities required of lecturers, which include knowledge, professional skills, and initiative. The results show that all three aspects contribute to professional competence, with initiative as the most dominant factor, especially as a role model in attitude and behavior. This confirms that an innovative and creative attitude to learning

is essential in improving lecturers' competence. This finding supports the opinion of Edison et al. (2016), who state that professional competence consists of knowledge, expertise, and initiative. Competence is defined as an individual's ability to carry out work correctly based on knowledge, skills, and attitudes, reflecting the criteria for lecturer competence in this study.

Lecturer performance in this study refers to respondents (lecturers) perception of the tasks that should be carried out in teaching, research, and community service. The results show that the indicators of education and teaching, research and development, and community service can shape the overall performance of lecturers. The main contribution comes from the education and teaching indicator, which shows that lecturers in Central Kalimantan prioritize this aspect more than other indicators. This result is reinforced by descriptive analysis, which proves that education and teaching are the main factors in providing quality teaching according to the learning design. This finding supports Purcanto's (2015) opinion, which states that performance consists of education, research, and community service and is defined as the achievement of work results that reflect achievement according to the role of lecturers as academic functional personnel.

This study found that applying Servant Leadership in Central Kalimantan Universities could not improve lecturer performance. This means that the attitude of leaders who serve, give trust, have credibility, and have a good vision does not directly impact lecturer performance in teaching, research, and community service. Empirically, the servant leadership model is not proven to directly improve the learning process or encourage lecturers' willingness to conduct research and community service. This finding differs from the results of other studies that show the importance of Servant Leadership in encouraging individual performance. This research is in line with the results of Liden et al. (2018), which state that Servant Leadership does not affect lecturer performance, but contradicts the research of Dennis & Bocarnea (2005), which states that this leadership model has a positive effect on lecturer performance.

The results of this study prove that the professional competence of lecturers significantly affects lecturer performance. Increased competence in knowledge, initiative attitude, and expertise impacts improving the quality of learning, the effectiveness of research implementation, and community service by lecturers. Lecturers initiative attitude, especially in communicating with students, is important in deepening students' understanding of the course. In addition, lecturer's expertise and knowledge are the main factors shaping professional competence. Improving the quality of lectures and scientific mastery can be more effective if lecturers continue to improve their expertise and knowledge in the field they teach. This finding supports Rianto's research

(2020), which states that competence has a significant influence on performance, thus reinforcing the importance of professional competence in improving lecturer performance.

6. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the previously described research results on improving lecturer performance through servant leadership and professional competence, it can be concluded that lecturer performance is determined by three main aspects: education and teaching, research, and community service, with education and teaching being the most dominant indicator. Lecturers organizational commitment is mostly influenced by affective, normative, and continuance commitment. Based on the servant leadership context, lecturer performance is mostly shaped by the leader's vision, credibility, trust, and service. Meanwhile, lecturers' professional competence is dominated by initiative, followed by professional expertise and knowledge, which shows the importance of developing proactive attitudes in improving lecturers' competence.

This study also found that servant leadership does not directly affect lecturers' performance in Central Kalimantan private universities. Lecturers tend to focus more on teaching and research, so servant leadership does not significantly improve learning, research, or community service performance. In contrast, the professional competence of lecturers is proven to have a direct influence on lecturer performance. Increased knowledge, professional expertise, and lecturers' initiative in improving communication and learning methods play an important role in improving Central Kalimantan private universities' teaching, research, and community service performance.

Based on the study results, it is recommended that science in the field of human resources be developed by emphasizing the importance of servant leadership and competence in improving lecturer performance. Educational institutions and individuals are expected to maintain and develop these two aspects. This study shows that improving the performance of lecturers in private universities in Central Kalimantan requires strengthening competencies and implementing more optimal servant leadership. In addition, this research can be a reference for further studies in other regions to expand understanding of the influence of competence and servant leadership on lecturer performance.

For practitioners, this research provides an overview of the importance of professional competence and servant leadership in improving the performance and organizational commitment of lecturers in private universities in Central Kalimantan. Lecturers are expected to continue to improve competence on an ongoing basis to adapt to organizational needs. In contrast, college leaders must apply servant leadership to create a productive work environment. For future researchers, this theme is relevant to be studied further

in different organizations to test organizational commitment as a mediating variable or add new variables, such as transformational leadership, to enrich the research results.

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